
24 Conservation State of the Deep-water Fish Fauna of the Dutch ABC-islands

Debrot, A. O., Robertson, D. R., Baldwin, C., van der Wal, J. T. and Vermeij, M. J. A. 2025. From: State of Nature Report for the Caribbean Netherlands, 2024. WUR report C001/25.

Status

With the term “deepwater” fish we here refer to fish species that have been documented at depths of 80 m or more. The literature providing documented deepwater fish records for the leeward Dutch islands (Aruba, Bonaire, Curaçao; ABC islands) is quite scant. Most studies are fairly recent and have been directed towards the description of the many small, new and long-overlooked species that the area is rich in. Table 1 provides a list of documented and expert-verified deep-water fish species records, for which island(s) they have been documented, their local documented depth (range), and their geographical distribution. We use six terms to classify the fish according to their geographical distribution. In the literature these terms are often used loosely by the many authors but for our assessment we more narrowly define the following seven-tiered geographic distributional terms as follows:

- 1) Inner Caribbean:** those parts of the inner Caribbean close to continental South America or Central America.
- 2) Greater Caribbean:** including the Gulf of Mexico, Bermuda the Bahamas and extending to the Guianas and Florida. In the literature this area is typically referred to as the West Central Atlantic.
- 3) Western Atlantic:** extending from the Greater Caribbean either northward beyond Florida and/or southwards from the Guyana's.
- 4) Eastern and Western Atlantic**
- 5) Circumtropical:** worldwide tropics and subtropical
- 6) Circumglobal:** worldwide temperate and tropical but also extending into colder and polar latitudes
- 7) Unknown:** too few samples to say anything

Many species of principally deepwater fish can occasionally occur in shallow water or may use shallow waters during parts of their life cycle (such as the deepwater snapper *Lutjanus vivanus* of which juveniles have been documented in 2 m of depth along the beach in Curaçao (Pors and Debrot, unpubl. data). Also, many shallow water species may occasionally be seen at greater depths. In this inventory, all records of fish confirmed at depths of 80 m or more were included, regardless of their known or presumed depth preferences.

Based on this effort, we here present a list of 144 confirmed species and 16 unique yet unidentified species-level taxa for depths of >80m based on 4,642 expert sightings or studied specimens (i.e., 160 species-level taxa). This adds 89 taxa to the list of 71 species-level taxa provided by Baldwin et al. (2018a), and of which 67 were described species and four were unique species-level taxa yet undescribed. In contrast to Baldwin et al. (2018a), we did not include any species that were not recorded at 80 m or deeper which corresponds to the upper boundary of the lower mesophotic zone (Baldwin et al., 2018a). Therefore, four species included by Baldwin et al. (2018a), were not included in the present list (*Chromis cyanea*, *C. multilineata*, *Haemulon flavolineatum* and *Stegastus partitus*).

This list is based on four principal sources. The first is the fishes caught by local fishermen throughout the years and brought to our attention for identification. Most of these identifications were done by

resident biologists (A. Debrot, I. Kristensen, I. Nagelkerken, L. Pors and M. Vermeij) of the Carmabi Foundation and relying principally on FAO fish identification sheets (Fischer, 1978). The second was a list of deepwater fishes observed and videoed (but otherwise unpublished) from a series of 24 submersible dives made in May 2000 by Harbor Branch, FLA, USA, down to depths of 900 m, off Curaçao, Bonaire and Aruba (Reed and Pomponi, 2000). The third principal source was the collection of dives by the Smithsonian Institution falling under the “DROP” project using the Curasub submarine to explore the reefs of Curaçao and Bonaire to maximum depths of about 300 m (Baldwin et al., 2018a). Finally, the fourth key source of records was the scientific literature, most publications of which were led by the Smithsonian Institution and pertain to species identifications coming forth from the Smithsonian “DROP” project. All difficult fish records were submitted to various specialists for identification so far as they deemed was possible.

Previously, Baldwin et al. (2018a) compiled a most extensive inventory of deepwater fish records for the island of Curaçao (and the southern Caribbean). They documented fish occurrence records for that island from depths of 40 meters and deeper and yielded a list of 71 species-level taxa (which then included four yet-unnamed species) based on 4,436 depth observations (Baldwin et al., 2018a). We here build on that initiative by compiling and listing 208 additional old as well as new previously published and unpublished deepwater fish records (ie: 4,642 records total) for an additional confirmation of 89 species-level taxa, of which 35 are added to the deepwater fish species list of records for Curaçao (and in some cases Bonaire or Aruba as well). However, 54 of these are, so far, exclusively listed as deepwater records for Bonaire and/or Aruba. Additional unconfirmed records suggest the presence of many more species but that would require better photographs or even specimens for detailed study and description.

Characteristics

Description:

Whereas a few papers assess the abyssal fish fauna (> 2000 m) of the Caribbean and adjacent tropical Atlantic (Anderson et al., 1987; Merrett & Fasham, 1998), fishes of the deep coral reef and upper continental and island slopes remain among the poorest-known marine faunas of the Caribbean (Williams & Williams, 2004; Garcia-Saes, 2010; Pinheiro et al., 2016; Baldwin et al., 2018a). Several authors have recently stressed the likely ecological and faunistic value of deep continental and island-slope habitats. Such deep habitats may function as key refugia for fish populations (e.g., Lesser et al. 2009), may possess unique coral assemblages (e.g. Meesters et al., 2013; Vermeij et al., 2003; Rocha et al., 2018) and many as yet undescribed species (e.g. Baldwin & Robertson, 2013; Baldwin et al., 2018b). Shelf-edge reefs have been highlighted as a priority for conservation of reef fish diversity in the tropical Atlantic (Olavo et al., 2011) but very few marine protected areas include such habitat.

For the description of new species, it is essential to be able to collect specimens and the ability to efficiently collect targeted specimens has been limited to the smallest species. Consequently, most new knowledge of the deepwater fishes has been developed for small collectable species (particularly gobies and serranids). The larger more vagile species, which include the commercially interesting species like deepwater snappers, groupers, tilefish and several others (like pomfrets and the swordfish) have hardly been documented in the literature even though they are either commonly caught by fishermen and are either casually or else with great likelihood known to occur

Table 1. Fish occurrence records for Aruba (A), Bonaire (B) and Curaçao (C) documented from depths of 80 meters and deeper, for 144 confirmed species and 16 unique yet unidentified species-level taxa based on 4,642 expert sightings or studied specimens. For all but the most-recently described or reassigned species we used the ECoF (Fricke et al., 2025) list of accepted scientific names and American Fisheries Society list of accepted common names (Page et al., 2023).

Species name	Common name (English / Papiamentu)	Documented range	Island occurrence Aruba (A), Bonaire (B) Curaçao (C)	Depths (m.)	Number of records
ACROPOMATIDAE					
<i>Synagrops bellus</i>	Blackmouth Bass	Atlantic & Western Pacific	B, C	100-422	3
<i>Verilus sordidus</i>	(Stèlchi di hundu)	Western Atlantic	B, C	100	2
ANTHIADIDAE					
<i>Anthias asperilinguis</i>		Western Atlantic	B, C	96-297	20
<i>Baldwinella cf vivanus</i>		Unknown	B, C	125-232	62
<i>Bathyanthias sp.</i>		Unknown	B	213-216	2
<i>Choranthias tenuis</i>	Threadnose Bass	Western Atlantic	B, C	90-301	25
<i>Hemanthias leptus</i>	Longtail Bass	Western Atlantic	B, C	114-183	4
<i>Plectranthias garrupellus</i>	Apricot Bass	Greater Caribbean	B	126	1
<i>Pronotogrammus martinicensis</i>	Roughtounge Bass	Western Atlantic	A, B, C	85-293	571
APOGONIDAE					
<i>Apogon gouldi</i>	Deepwater Cardinalfish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	102-157	20
<i>Apogon pillionatus</i>	Broadsaddle Cardinalfish	Western Atlantic	B	122-140	1
<i>Apogon pseudomaculatus</i>	Twospot Cardinalfish	Western Atlantic	B	114	2
<i>Paroncheilus affinis</i>	Bigtooth Cardinalfish	Eastern & Western Central Atlantic	B, C	90-154	9
AULOPIDAE					
<i>Aulopus filamentosus</i>	Yellowfin Aulopus	Eastern & Western Atl.	C	100-150	1
<i>Saurida normani</i>	Shortjaw Lizardfish	Western Atlantic	B	200-250	1
BALISTIDAE					
<i>Xanthichthys ringens</i>	Sargassum triggerfish (Pishi porko shinishi)	Western Atlantic	B, C	49-105	17
BATHYCLUPEIDAE					
<i>Neobathyclupea cf. argentea</i>	Silver Deep-sea Herring	Western Atlantic	C	633-665	2
BRAMIDAE					
<i>Eumegistus brevorti</i>	Tropical Pomfret (Pamper di hundu)	Western Atlantic	B, C	300-650	4
BYTHIDAE					
<i>Stygnobrotula latebricola</i>	Black Brotula	Western Atlantic	B	114-137	1
CALLIONYMIDAE					
<i>Synchiropus agassizii</i>	Spotfin Dragonet	Western Atlantic	C	236-304	7
CAPROIDAE					
<i>Antigonia capros</i>	Deepbody Boarfish	Circumtropical	B, C	100-299	84
<i>Antigonia sp.</i>	Boarfish sp.	Greater Caribbean	C	NA	1
CARANGIDAE					
<i>Caranx bartholomaei</i>	Yellow Jack (Sareu)	Western Atlantic	B	93	1
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Black Jack (Korkobá pretu)	Circumtropical	A, C	<144	3
<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Almaco Jack (Kabijou)	Circumglobal	B, C	115-190	6
CETORHINIDAE					
<i>Cetorhinus maximus</i>	Basking Shark	Cosmopolitan	A	0	2
CHAETODONTIDAE					
<i>Chaetodon capistratus</i>	Foureye Butterflyfish	Western Atlantic	C	<40-101	17
<i>Chaetodon sedentarius</i>	Reef Butterflyfish	Western Atlantic	B	85-112	3
<i>Chaetodon striatus</i>	Banded Butterflyfish (Makamba marinir)	Western Atlantic	B	84	1
<i>Prognathodes aculeatus</i>	Longsnout Butterflyfish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	88-149	5

<i>Prognathodes guyanensis</i>	Guyana Butterflyfish	Western Atlantic	B, C	88-216	32
CHAUNACIDAE					
<i>Chaunax cf suttkusi</i>	Pale-cavity Gaper	Eastern & Western Atl.	C	610	1
<i>Chaunax pictus</i>	Uniform Gaper	Eastern & Western Atl.	C	247-307	6
CONGRIDAE					
<i>Conger triporiceps</i>	Manytooth conger (Conglá)	Western Atlantic	C	120-150	0
DALATIIDAE					
<i>Scyliorhinus hesperius</i>	White-saddled Cat Shark	Greater Caribbean	B, C	200-220	4
EPIGONIDAE					
<i>Epigonus gemma</i>		Southern Caribbean	C	156-309	5
<i>Epigonus hexacanthus</i>		Southern Caribbean	C	156-297	8
<i>Epigonus sp.</i>	Deepwater cardinalfish sp.		C	357-369	3
<i>Sphyaenops bairdianus</i>	Triple spine Deepwater Cardinalfish	Worldwide temperate & tropical	C	265-280	6
EPINEPHELIDAE					
<i>Cephalopholis cruentata</i>	Grasby (Purunchi)	Western Atlantic	B, C	<40-135	37
<i>Epinephelus morio</i>	Red Grouper (Meru)	Western Atlantic	A	3-140	1
<i>Gonioplectrus hispanus</i>	Spanish Flag (Bandera spañó)	Western Atlantic	B, C	101-224	58
<i>Hyporthodus niveatus</i>	Snowy Grouper (Djampou)	Western Atlantic	B	175-300	5
<i>Mycteroperca bonaci</i>	Black Grouper (Djampou)	Western Atlantic	C, B	91	2
<i>Paranthias furcifer</i>	Atlantic Creolefish (Mahawa, Stèlchi)	Eastern & Western Atl.	C, B	<40-110	248
FISTULARIIDAE					
<i>Fistularia petimba</i>	Red Cornetfish	Worldwide temperate & tropical	C	263	1
<i>Fistularia sp.</i>	Cornetfish sp.		B	175-178	2
GEMPYLIDAE					
<i>Epinnula magistralis</i>	Domine	Greater Caribbean	A	NA	1
<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Snake Mackerel	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	C	8	1
<i>Nesiarchus nasutus</i>	Black Gemfish	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	C	NA	1
<i>Promethichthys prometheus</i>	Roudi Escolar (Kaka leu leu)	Worldwide tropical & subtropical	C	120-150	1
<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Oilfish (Kaka sin sinti)	Worldwide tropical & subtropical	B, C	100-150	3
GOBIIDAE					
<i>Antilligobius nikkiae</i>	Sabre Goby	Caribbean	B, C	82-205	259
<i>Bollmannia eigenmannorum</i>	Shelf Goby	Greater Caribbean	B	84	1
<i>Coryphopterus curasub</i>	Yellow-spotted Sand-goby	Southern Caribbean	B, C	70-163	7
<i>Palatogobius incendius</i>	Ember Goby	Greater Caribbean	B, C	114-205	326
<i>Priolepis hipoliti</i>	Rusty Goby	Greater Caribbean	B	115-117	2
<i>Psilotris laurae</i>	Thin-barred Goby	Southern Caribbean	B	121-162	3
<i>Psilotris vantasselli</i>	Clementine Split-fin Goby	Greater Caribbean	B	149-159	1
<i>Ptereleotris helenae</i>	Hovering Dartfish	Western Atlantic	B, C	<40-127	29
<i>Robinsichthys nigrimarginatus</i>	Black-margined Goby	Southern Caribbean	C	229	0
<i>Undescribed goby</i>	Goby sp.	Southern Caribbean	B	142-158	3
<i>Varicus cephalocellatus</i>	Ocellated Split-fin Goby	Southern Caribbean	B	121-305	4
<i>Varicus decorum</i>	Decorated Split-fin Goby	Southern Caribbean	B, C	159-164	4
<i>Varicus lacerta</i>	Godzilla Goby	Southern Caribbean	C	129-143	6
<i>Varicus veliguttatus</i>	Spotted sail-Goby	Greater Caribbean	C	152-225	1
GRAMMATIDAE					

<i>Lipogramma barrettorum</i>	Blue-spotted Basslet	Southern Caribbean	C	123-161	6
<i>Lipogramma evides</i>	Banded Basslet	Greater Caribbean	B, C	124-265	59
<i>Lipogramma haberorum</i>	Yellow-banded Basslet	Southern Caribbean	C	152-233	3
<i>Lipogramma klayi</i>	Bicolor Basslet	Greater Caribbean	B, C	79-114	42
<i>Lipogramma levinsoni</i>	Hourglass Basslet	Greater Caribbean	B, C	111-153	13
<i>Lipogramma schrieri</i>	Maori Basslet	Southern Caribbean	C	173-207	6
GRAMMICOLEPIDIDAE					
<i>Grammicolepis brachiusculus</i>	Thorny Tinseltail	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	B	463-650	2
GRAMMISTIDAE					
<i>Jeboehkia gladifer</i>	Bladefin Basslet	Western Caribbean	B, C	125-203	57
<i>Rypticus cf. randalli</i>	Plain Soapfish	Western Atlantic	B	84	1
<i>Rypticus saponaceus</i>	Greater Soapfish, Habon	Eastern & Western Atl.	B	114	1
HAEMULIDAE					
<i>Haemulon striatum</i>	Striped Grunt	Western Atlantic	B, C	53-107	34
<i>Haemulon vittatum</i>	Boga, Traki traki	Western Atlantic	C	<40-105	17
HEXANCHIDAE					
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Bluntnose Sixgill Shark	Eastern & Western Atl.	B, C	>100	2
<i>Hexanchus vitulus</i>	Atlantic Sixgill Shark (Tribon brabu)	Circumglobal	B, C	100-350	3
HOLOCENTRIDAE					
<i>Corniger spinosus</i>	Spineycheek Soldierfish	Western Atlantic	C	137-238	11
<i>Myripristis jacobus</i>	Blackbar Soldierfish (Barí di klabu)	Eastern & Western Atl.	C	<40-83	13
<i>Neoniphon marianus</i>	Longjaw Squirrelfish (Korá kandèl)	Greater Caribbean	C	53-101	37
<i>Ostichthys trachypoma</i>	Bigeye Soldierfish	Western Atlantic	B, C	100-287	105
IPNOPIDAE					
<i>Bathypterois spec.</i>	Deep-sea tripod fish sp.		B	916	2
LABRIDAE					
<i>Bodianus parrae</i>	Creole Wrasse	Greater Caribbean	C	<40-95	287
<i>Decodon puellaris</i>	Red Hogfish (Pewchi di hundu)	Western Atlantic	B, C	87-231	12
<i>Decodon sp2</i>			B	116-161	3
<i>Halichoeres bathyphilus</i>	Greenband Wrasse	Western Atlantic	B	116	1
<i>Polyplepion gilmorei</i>	Red-barred Wrasse	Western Atlantic	C	219-272	4
LABRISOMIDAE					
<i>Haptoclinus dropi</i>	Four-fin Blenny	Southern Caribbean	C	157-167	2
<i>Starksia sp.</i>			B	84-226	1
LATILIDAE					
<i>Caulolatilus cyanops</i>	Blackline Tilefish (Tumba)	Western Atlantic	B	200-350	3
<i>Caulolatilus dooleyi</i>	Bankslope Tilefish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	200-350	3
<i>Caulolatilus guppyi</i>	Reticulated Tilefish	Southern Caribbean	A	90	1
<i>Caulolatilus williamsi</i>	Yellowbar Tilefish (Donseo)	Greater Caribbean	B, C	200-350	4
LIOPROPOMATIDAE					
<i>Liopropoma aberrans</i>	Eyestripe Basslet	Greater Caribbean	B, C	98-241	39
<i>Liopropoma carmabi</i>	Candy Basslet (Carmabivis)	Greater Caribbean	B	84	1
<i>Liopropoma mowbrayi</i>	Cave Basslet	Greater Caribbean	B, C	56-133	112
<i>Liopropoma olneyi</i>	Yellow-spotted Basslet	Greater Caribbean	B, C	110-229	83
<i>Liopropoma santi</i>	Spot-tail golden Basslet	Southern Caribbean	C	182-209	3
LUTJANIDAE					
<i>Etelis oculatus</i>	Queen Snapper (Sabonèchi)	Western Atlantic	B, C	200-500	6
<i>Lutjanus apodus</i>	Schoolmaster (Bèrs)	Western Atlantic	B	146	1

<i>Lutjanus buccanella</i>	Blackfin Snapper (Korá hala pretu)	Western Atlantic	B, C	91-163	4
<i>Lutjanus purpureus</i>	Caribbean Red Snapper (Korá)	Western Atlantic	C	>100	1
<i>Lutjanus vivanus</i>	Silk Snapper (Shiriki)	Western Atlantic	C	>100	1
<i>Ocyurus chrysurus</i>	Yellowtail Snapper (Grastèlchi di piedra)	Western Atlantic	B	95-116	1
<i>Pristipomoides aquilonaris</i>	Wrenchman (Rondu)	Western Atlantic	B	216	1
<i>Pristipomoides freemani</i>	Slender Wrenchman	Western Atlantic	B	197	1
<i>Pristipomoides macrophthalmus</i>	Cardinal Snapper	Western Atlantic	C	210-290	1
MACROURIDAE					
<i>Coryphaenoides sp.</i>	Grenadier sp.		C	711	1
<i>Macrouridae sp.</i>	Grenadier sp.		B	765	1
<i>Malacocephalus cf. laevis</i>	Velvet Grenadier	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	C	740	1
<i>Nezumia cf. aequalis</i>	Atlantic Blacktip Grenadier	Eastern & Western Atl.	C	608	1
MORIDAE					
<i>Physiculus fulvus</i>	Metallic Codling	Western Atlantic	A, B	151-297	4
MURAENIDAE					
<i>Gymnothorax maderensis</i>	Sharktooth Moray (Kolebra)	Eastern & Western Atl.	A, B, C	109-302	5
<i>Gymnothorax moringa</i>	Spotted Moray (Kolebra)	Western Atlantic	B	113	1
<i>Gymnothorax ocellatus</i>	Ocellated Moray (Kolebra)	Western Atlantic	B	187-194	1
OGCOEPHALIDAE					
<i>Ogcocephalus parvus</i>	Roughback Batfish (Palomba di awa)	Western Atlantic	B, C	100-161	2
PARALICHTHYIDAE					
<i>Citharichthys dinoceros</i>	Spined Whiff	Western Atlantic	B	185	1
PENTANCHIDAE					
<i>Apristurus sp.</i>	Deepwater Cat Shark sp.		B	100-919	3
<i>Parmaturus sp.</i>	Cat Shark	Western Atlantic	B	NA	1
PERCOPHIDAE					
<i>Chrionema squamentum</i>	Scalychin Flathead	Greater Caribbean	B, C	162-306	186
PERISTEDIIDAE					
<i>Peristedion brevirostre</i>	Flathead Armored Searobin (Sabu sèiskiel)	Greater Caribbean	B	180-300	4
<i>Peristedion cf. imberbe</i>	Tropical Armored Slender Searobin	Western Atlantic	C	NA	1
POLYMIXIIDAE					
<i>Polymixia sp.</i>	Beardfish sp.		B, C	300-380	3
POMACANTHIDAE					
<i>Centropyge argi</i>	Cherubfish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	63-99	42
<i>Holacanthus ciliaris</i>	Queen Angelfish	Western Atlantic	B	84	1
<i>Pomacanthus paru</i>	French Angelfish (Sheu)	Eastern & Western Atl.	B	91	1
POMACENTRIDAE					
<i>Chromis cf. scotti</i>	Purple Reeffish	Western Atlantic	B, C	49-101	85
<i>Chromis insolata</i>	Sunshinefish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	40-110	215
<i>Chromis vanbebberae</i>	Whitetail Reeffish	Western Atlantic	C	49-178	7
PRIACANTHIDAE					
<i>Pristigenys alta</i>	Short Bigeye	Western Atlantic	B	73-183	14
REGALECIDAE					
<i>Regalecus glesne</i>	Oarfish	Circumglobal	C	0	1
SCIAENIDAE					

<i>Eques lanceolatus</i>	Jackknife-fish (Rei di lamán)	Western Atlantic	B	100-160	7
SCOMBROPIDAE					
<i>Scombrops oculatus</i>	Gnome Fish	Greater Caribbean	C	NA	1
SCORPAENIDAE					
<i>Pontinus castor</i>	Longsnout Scorpionfish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	87-243	25
<i>Pontinus longispinis</i>	Longspine Scorpionfish	Western Atlantic	B, C	237-343	3
<i>Pontinus nematophthalmus</i>	Spinythroat Scorpionfish	Western Atlantic	B, C	132-302	24
<i>Pterois volitans</i>	Lionfish	Pacific Ocean	B	85-182	9
<i>Scorpaena agassizii</i>	Longfin Scorpionfish	Western Atlantic	B	174-204	2
<i>Scorpaenodes barrybrowni</i>	Stellate Scorpionfish	Greater Caribbean	B, C	114-154	8
SERRANIDAE					
<i>Bullisichthys caribbaeus</i>	Pugnose Bass	Greater Caribbean	B, C	81-134	263
<i>Serranus atrobranchus</i>	Blackear Bass	Western Atlantic	B	122-140	1
<i>Serranus chionaraia</i>	Snow Bass	Greater Caribbean	B	83-95	3
<i>Serranus fuscus</i>	Twospot Seabass	Western Atlantic	C	48-245	13
<i>Serranus luciopercanus</i>	Crosshatch Bass	Greater Caribbean	B, C	61-129	72
<i>Serranus notospilus</i>	Saddle Bass	Greater Caribbean	B, C	107-234	111
<i>Serranus phoebe</i>	Tattler (Vrumoe)	Western Atlantic	B, C	83-186	35
<i>Serranus tortugarum</i>	Chalk Bass	Greater Caribbean	B	82	1
SQUALIDAE					
<i>Squalus cubensis</i>	Cuban Dogfish	Western Atlantic	C	293	2
STOMIIDAE					
<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	Manylight Viperfish	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	C	>100	2
SYMPHSANODONTIDAE					
<i>Symphysanodon berryi</i>	Slope Bass	Eastern & Western Atl.c	C	126-296	117
<i>Symphysanodon octoactinus</i>	Insular Bunquelovely	Greater Caribbean	B, C	133-167	155
SYNODONTIDAE					
<i>Synodontidae sp.</i>	Lizardfish sp.		b	150-331	2
TETRAODONTIDAE					
<i>Canthigaster jamestyeri</i>	Goldface Toby	Western Atlantic	B, C	70-152	117
<i>Canthigaster rostrata</i>	Sharpnose Puffer	Western Atlantic	B	116	1
<i>Sphoeroides pachygaster</i>	Blunthead Puffer (Fugu)	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	B, C	200	2
TRACHICHTYIDAE					
<i>Gephyroberyx darwinii</i>	Big Roughy	Cosmopolitan	B, C	266-562	4
<i>Hoplostethus mediterraneus</i>	Silver Roughy	Cosmopolitan	C	360	1
<i>Hoplostethus sp.</i>	Roughy sp.		B, C	114-319	3
TRICANTHODIDAE					
<i>Hollardia meadi</i>	Spotted Spikefish	Western Atlantic	B	176-305	1
TRICHIURIDAE					
<i>Evoxymetopon taeniatus</i>	Channel Scabbardfish (Machete)	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	B	0	1
<i>Trichiurus lepturus</i>	Atlantic Cutlassfish (Cachicang, Guepi baraháns)	Worldwide subtropical & tropical	C	0	1
TRIGLIDAE					
<i>Bellator brachyichir</i>	Shortfin Searobin	Western Atlantic	B, C	119-245	14
<i>Bellator egretta</i>	Streamer Searobin	Western Atlantic	B, C	176-232	8
<i>Bellator sp.</i>	Searobin sp.		B	150-220	1
XIPHIIDAE					

Isl.occ. = Island occurrence; n.recs = number of records.

The southern Caribbean has been demonstrated to be a separate biogeographic province for different animal groups among which are molluscs (Diaz, 1995) and fishes (Spalding, 2007; Robertson & Cramer, 2014). Consequently, many described species are principally or strictly limited to the southern and or western Caribbean. These species include both long-described shallow and recently described deepwater species. The fauna also may include several unique and possibly range-restricted elasmobranchs (e.g. *Apristurus* spp., Table 1) but obtaining actual specimens for detailed study is difficult. Consequently, this interesting component of the deep-water fish fauna remains very poorly known.

Of all taxa distinguished, something can be said about their known geographical distribution for 156 species (Fig. 1). Of these, 16 species (10%) appear to be endemic to a small inner portion of the Caribbean Sea, 36 (23%) appear endemic to the Greater Caribbean, while 67 (43%) are limited to the Western Atlantic. More widely distributed species, extending across the Atlantic and beyond amounted to 35 species (23%). Overall, the results show the strong regional affinities of the fish fauna and a high proportion of species with a highly range-restricted (i.e.. "endemic") distribution.

The geographic position of the Dutch leeward islands off the northeast coast of south America has remained unchanged since the upper Miocene (7-9 Ma) (Iturralde-Vinent, 2006). This placed these islands in a strategic upstream location with respect to current flows within the Caribbean and likely allowed them to play an exceptional role for dispersal of marine life throughout the region, even long before the isthmus of Panama fully closed during the Pliocene-Holocene epochs (3.7-0 Ma) (Iturralde-Vinent, 2006). Their location outside the main Western Atlantic hurricane zone, further reduces exposure to annual hurricane risk while their separation from the mainland of South America provides protection from continental stress factors of freshwater and sediment loads that can strongly limit reef development (Weil, 2003).

Figure 1. Known geographical distribution of the fish species documented (to verified or almost certain species level "cf") at depths of 80 m or more around the leeward Dutch Caribbean islands of Aruba, Bonaire and Curaçao. Relative Importance within the Caribbean: High.

Finally, their location close to the main upwelling zone of the Caribbean also appears to explain their unique protection from the worst impacts of regional sea-surface warming (Eakin et al., 2010), The long-lasting favourable conditions for reef growth likely underpin their role as a storehouse of coral reef-associated biodiversity that continues to be documented. Not surprisingly then, the southern

Caribbean is very interesting from a biogeographic perspective as it has been recognized as a distinct marine biogeographic province for fish diversity (Spalding 2007; Robertson & Cramer 2014) and more than a dozen new species have recently been described for these islands (Baldwin et al., 2016a; 2016b; 2018b; 2023; Baldwin & Robertson, 2013; 2014; 2015; Carvalho-Filho et al., 2023; McFarland et al., 2020; Okamoto et al., 2024; Tornabene and Baldwin, 2017; 2019; Tornabene et al., 2016a; 2016b; 2023).

Ecological aspects

Habitat: Baldwin et al. (2018a) distinguish large differences in deepwater fish faunas of the upper mesophotic (40-79 m), the lower mesophotic (80-129) and the upper rariphotic (130-189 m) and lower rariphotic (190-309m) zones. The strongest partition between these four different faunas occurs between the mesophotic and rariphotic zones and between the upper and lower rariphotic zones (Baldwin et al., 2018a). The main differences between these zones are defined by temperature (e.g.: thermocline), light (which influences photosynthesis) and food and energy availability, as at depths of beyond 200 m the input of food becomes limited (Woolley et al., 2016). Consequently, many mesopelagic fish and plankton species will migrate vertically on a diurnal basis to feed in the shallower food-rich waters typically at night (Benoit-Bird and Moline, 2021).

Food: Herbivorous fish species are absent in the deep mesophotic zone or deeper (80 m and beyond). Almost all species are either piscivores, benthic invertivores or planktivores, this includes the four deep-reef pomacentrids of the genus *Chromis* which are all planktivorous.

Minimum viable population size: Unknown

For fish species, minimum viable population sizes have not yet been meaningfully explored. This concept is best applied to terrestrial species but even for those there are many caveats and limitations (Traill et al., 2007; Ottburg and van Swaay, 2014).

Present Distribution and Reference Values

The distribution of fish species is here recorded in terms of their: a) documented depth ranges for these islands; b) documented island occurrences and also: c) the documented geographical range for each species. The documented depth ranges for many species for the islands is based on only few confirmed records. Therefore, many species can be expected to have broader depth ranges than this limited data set would suggest (and as is also likely from the depth distributions known for many of the same species from elsewhere). The most reliable local depth ranges are provided for several species (Baldwin et al., 2018a) based on much larger sample sizes. At present, the island occurrence of different species is seriously under-represented due to the low level of sampling, especially for Aruba. With more extensive and judicious observation, probably most species will eventually be able to be confirmed for all three islands. Finally, the most reliable information on distribution is the data on geographic distribution. The only exception would be the many newly described and possibly range-restricted small species (mainly gobies and serranids), which may be ultimately found to have a wider distribution once deepwater surveys from different parts of the Caribbean become more widely available.

Assessment of National Conservation State

Aside from the scant species records for most species, little is known about the local or international Conservation State of most species. However, four of the deepwater sharks documented from the ABC-islands have a IUCN Red List threatened classification. These are *Cetorhinus maximus* (Endangered), *Hexanchus griseus* and *H. vitulus* (Near Threatened) and *Parmaturus angelae* (Vulnerable). *Scylorhinus hesperius* and *Squalus cubensis* are classified as "Least Concern".

In addition, the heavily fished swordfish, *Xiphius gladius*, and grouper *Mycteroperca bonaci* have a Near Threatened listing while the groupers *Epinephelus morio* and *Hyporthodus niveatus* are listed as Vulnerable by the IUCN. The status of all other species is either Least Concern or Unknown due to lack of information.

Trends in the Caribbean Netherlands: Unfavourable-inadequate

Trends for deepwater species in the Caribbean Netherlands are unknown, but for most of the small deepwater species no serious immediate threats are really known but this surely must be ascribed to the lack of research and not to the lack of serious yet unknown threats.

Recent developments: Description of many new deepwater species

Many new and possibly unique species have been recently described (Baldwin et al., 2016a, 2016b, 2018b; Baldwin and Robertson, 2013; 2014; 2015; McFarland et al., 2020; Tornabene and Baldwin, 2017; 2019; Tornabene et al., 2016a; 2016b; Okamoto et al., 2024). It remains to be seen how these species are distributed in the southern Caribbean or rest of the region. These mostly involve a whole number of small collectable serranids and gobies. However, there is considerable untapped potential for possibly unique range-restricted deep-water sharks as well (*Apristurus* spp., *Isistius* spp.) (Debrot et al., 2014a).

Assessment of distribution: Favourable

Most species records are for Curaçao and Bonaire while the least are for Aruba. This is likely largely based on the much greater sampling effort expended around Curaçao and Bonaire than around Aruba (or for that matter most elsewhere in the southern Caribbean). The distribution of individual species is likely more extensive than based on this limited sampling effort, and thus favourable.

Assessment of population: Favourable

Quantitative assessments at community or population levels are very problematic because quantitative fish surveys at depth are difficult to obtain. Such assessments will only become available once directed deepwater ROV transects or drop data become available. At present Wageningen Marine Science is working with drones to obtain quantitative insights into the population density, size-structure and relative distribution of commercially targeted fish stocks of the Saba Bank but such work has yet to commence for the fish stocks of Bonaire. The population sizes of most species around the leeward Dutch Caribbean are likely to be favourable as the habitats are intact and fishing pressure is likely low or zero on most species.

Assessment of habitat: Favourable

Some insight is available regarding the local depth distribution of each species. For most species little local knowledge is available on other aspects of habitat use or dependence.

Table 2. Summary overview of the status of the deep-water fish fauna of the leeward Caribbean Netherlands in terms of different conservations aspects.

Aspect deep water fish fauna	2024
Distribution	Favourable
Population size	Favourable
Habitat	Favourable
Future prospects	Unfavourable-inadequate
Overall Assessment of Conservation State	Unfavourable-inadequate

Comparison to the 2018 State of Nature report

This is the first CS assessment made for the deepwater fishes of the Leeward Caribbean Netherlands and hence no comparison can be made to any earlier report.

Goals for the national conservation objective

The goals as outlined in the management plan for the Exclusive Economic Zone of the Dutch Caribbean (Meesters et al., 2010) remain pertinent. These were to: a) assemble, review and assess existing literature and data on the Dutch Caribbean deep sea and adjacent areas; b) encourage the organization of a deep-sea expedition to collect, describe and document the biodiversity, possibly coupled with preliminary bioprospecting. Several initial steps in this have thus been taken. As part of action point b, in 2013 the Ministry of Economic Affairs financed a 2-day deep-reef submersible exploration in the coastal waters of Bonaire during which about 15 species likely new to science (none of which were fish) were collected (Becking & Meesters, 2014). In addition, some preliminary deep-water exploration has been done on the Saba Bank (van Duyl & Meesters, 2020; Humphreys et al., 2022).

Key threats and management implications

Unknown but likely worse than until recently expected

Loiseau et al. (2024) have most recently discovered that a much larger proportion of marine fish than expected (about 25%) should be regarded as seriously threatened. For the Caribbean Netherlands this remains unknown. While so far only for one endemic deep reef fish species have authors raised conservation concerns due to predation by an invasive species (Tornabene and Baldwin, 2017) the situation could well be alarming for many species. However, this remains unknown due to the lack of research. The mesophotic and rariphotic deepwater habitats in question do suffer high levels of litter pollution (Debrot et al., 2014b) but the impacts of litter pollution on deep-water fishes also have not been assessed.

For the larger commercially interesting species, several have been internationally overfished to the point at which their Conservation State has become of concern (particularly deepwater snappers, groupers and sharks). Several of these species may be overfished around the ABC-islands particularly due to the generally limited surface area of habitat available which means that overfishing can quickly occur. While overfishing of the shallower reef-associated fish stocks around these islands is well documented (Debrot and Criens, 2005; Debrot and de Graaf, 2018; Vermeij et al., 2019) the status of deepwater fish stocks is very poorly documented. More work is recommended to assess the potential of these stocks to support sustainable fisheries (Debrot et al., 2019). More generally it is known that deepwater fish species often are long-lived, with slow growth rates and can only support limited fishing pressure (Norse et al., 2012). Finally, the potential impact of climate change that may possibly affect water temperatures and oxygen concentrations at depth, as well as current patterns, must be kept in mind but are yet unknown.

Data quality and completeness

Apart from the seminal work by Metzelaar (1922), there are very few comprehensive treatments of the fish fauna of the Dutch ABC islands. The first major treatment of the groupers and snappers for the Dutch Caribbean is given by Nagelkerken (1981). In it he presents information on a total of 14 groupers and 12 snappers, most of which are shallow water species. Baldwin et al. (2018a) recently compiled an extensive inventory of deepwater fish records for the island of Curaçao (and the southern Caribbean) and Robertson et al. (2022) point out the crucial role that submersibles have and will need to play in developing more and better information on deepwater fish faunas.

Nevertheless, in general, very little is known about the local occurrence and ecology of deepwater fishes in the southern Caribbean and most deepwater species listed elsewhere for the Dutch Caribbean are not based on actual documented records but based on interpolation. The ABC-islands get included as "range" islands based on the combination of two main arguments. These are that: a) if a species is listed for location A and B, it is logical to infer that it also occurs at the points (or countries) in between. so long as b) suitable habitat is also present. Our purpose here was hence to compile

documented and expert-verified records of deepwater fish occurrences for the ABC-islands as a first step towards a better understanding of the represented biodiversity and fisheries potential.

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